

Data S1B. Seeds (*Stemona mairei*) discarded by *Pheidole nodus* outside of their nest. (B') Red pins: first day (seeds thrown out one day after they enter the nest), white pins: second day, blue pins: third day. (B'') Seeds with intact elaiosomes (left) and seeds consumed by ants (elaiosomes removed, right). (B''') Seedlings sprouting near ant nests.

Data S1D. Comparison of the carrying distance of seeds robbed by fly *B. varicolor* (D') and final dispersal distance of the robbed seeds (D'') in four bioassays. The short horizontal line in Violin Plots indicates the mean; * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$.

Data S1E. Linear regression analysis of the carrying distance of seeds robbed by *B. varicolor* and the final dispersal distance of the robbed seeds in large fly & large seed.

Data S1F. Different ant species acting as dispersers in bioassays. (F', F'''''), *Pheidole nodus* dispersing *Stemona mairei* and *Gymnosporia berberoides* seeds, respectively. (F'', F''''''') *Aphaenogaster beccarii*. (F''', F''''''''') *Camponotus japonicus*. (F''''') *Odontomachus monticola*. (F''''''''') *Leptogenys kitteli*.

Data S1G. Comparison of the species and proportion of ants involved in seed dispersal in the primary and secondary ant nests with/without the presence of *B. varicolor*.

Data S1J. Global distribution map of myrmecochory and *Bengalia* (with robbery behaviour). (J')

The distribution of 13 species of *Bengalia* with robbery behaviour has been reported. (J'') Biogeographical distribution of myrmecochory (the numbers represent the number of evolutionary origins of myrmecochorous plant in each biogeographic region, modified from ref. S10), the oblique patterns indicate the overlapping distribution of myrmecochory and *Bengalia*.